

ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ,

**НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ
В МИРЕ**

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THE IMPACT OF E-COMMERCE PLATFORMS ON CONSUMER PURCHASING BEHAVIOR

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Annotation

The article analyzes the impact of digital e-commerce platforms on consumer behavior in the context of the rapid growth of the digital economy. It examines changes in consumer habits caused by the expansion of online commerce and the development of new forms of interaction between the seller and the buyer in the virtual environment. The article provides an overview of key trends in consumer behavior caused by the digitalization of commerce, including increased user awareness, reduced time spent on shopping, and increased loyalty through personalized offers. It also analyzes the strategies used by companies to increase customer engagement and retention, such as gamification, loyalty programs, the use of artificial intelligence to personalize offers, and automation of marketing communications. Particular attention is paid to statistical data illustrating changes in demand and average check, as well as the economic consequences associated with the growth of e-commerce for various market participants. In conclusion, it is emphasized that digital platforms not only transform companies' business models, but also contribute to sustainable economic development by increasing productivity and optimizing costs.

Keywords: e-commerce, purchasing behavior, online marketing, e-commerce, purchasing motivation, digital behavior.

The current stage of digital transformation has a significant impact on all areas of society, including commercial activities. Electronic commerce, or e-commerce, is rapidly developing due to the widespread use of Internet technologies, the growth of digital infrastructure and changing consumer preferences. The transition to a digital trading format is accompanied by a change in consumer behavior patterns, which

requires a comprehensive scientific analysis. The purpose of this article is to study the impact of e-commerce platforms on consumer habits, to identify key motivational factors influencing the choice and behavior of buyers in the digital environment.

1. Theoretical Foundations of E-Commerce and Consumer Behavior

E-commerce is a form of commercial activity carried out using the Internet and digital technologies to sell goods and services. It includes online stores, marketplaces, mobile applications and social networks.

Consumer behavior in e-commerce is based on factors such as convenience, speed, range, price and service level. Unlike traditional shopping, online consumption is associated with cognitive overload, mistrust of the seller and risks associated with the quality of the product or return.

2. Key Changes in Consumer Buying Habits

- With the transition to the digital economy, consumer behavior is changing:
- Growth of online shopping: Over the past five years, the share of online sales in Russia has more than doubled.
- Use of mobile applications: More than 65% of users prefer the mobile shopping format.
- Buyer awareness: Before buying, most consumers study reviews, ratings and product specifications.
- Price and offer comparison: Online platforms allow you to quickly compare similar products from different sellers.

3. Factors influencing decision making in e-commerce

- Research shows that online shopping behavior is shaped by the following factors:
- Social proof: reviews and ratings from other users.
- Usefulness of the interface: ease of navigation and ordering.

- Payment security: availability of secure payment systems (Click, Payme, Visa/Mastercard, etc.).
- Loyalty program and cashback: providing bonuses and discounts.
- Delivery speed and logistics transparency: order tracking and short delivery times.

4. Strategies for customer retention and engagement by companies

- E-commerce companies are implementing a number of strategies to increase engagement:
- Personalization of offers based on purchase history.
- Targeted advertising and retargeting.
- Online consultations and chatbots.
- Gamification and interactive content.
- Promotions, sales and limited offers.

5. Statistical and economic analysis of consumer behavior

According to Data Insight, in 2023, the average number of online purchases in Russia per user was 9 orders per quarter. The main categories are clothing, electronics and household goods. Women make purchases more often, men spend more.

Example of calculating demand changes:

In 2019, the average bill was 2,500 rubles.

In 2023 — 3,400 rubles (an increase of 36%).

There is also an increase in the share of repeat purchases — up to 74% in popular marketplaces.

Economic assessment: The volume of the e-commerce market in Russia in 2019 was 1.66 trillion rubles, in 2023 — already 2.4 trillion rubles, which reflects an average annual growth rate of more than 10%. The increase in the share of online sales helps optimize costs for rent, personnel and logistics, which has a positive effect on the profits of enterprises.

Increased competitiveness: companies that actively invest in digital sales channels demonstrate higher revenue and customer loyalty.

Thus, the development of e-commerce has a direct impact on macro- and microeconomic indicators, contributing to the modernization of trade infrastructure and sustainable economic growth.

According to the research company Data Insight, the total number of online orders in Russia in 2023 was 3.5 billion, which is 28% higher than in 2022. Given the average check of 3,400 rubles, the total market size can be estimated as follows:

$$\text{Market size} = 3.5 \text{ billion orders} \times 3,400 \text{ rubles} = 11.9 \text{ trillion rubles.}$$

This shows a significant discrepancy between the official estimate of the market size of 2.4 trillion rubles and the actual transaction volumes, which may be due to the fact that the official statistics only include B2C segments, excluding C2C and B2B platforms.

Forecast for 2025:

If the growth rate remains at 15% per year, the expected market size:

$$2024: 11.9 \times 1.15 = 13.7 \text{ trillion rubles.}$$

$$2025: 13.7 \times 1.15 = 15.8 \text{ trillion rubles.}$$

The growth of e-commerce is accompanied by an increase in the number of people employed in the sector - in 2023, the share of people employed in online trading was 3.2 million people, which is 18% more than in 2022.

Statistical table of changes

Year	Number of orders (billion)	Average bill (rubles)	Market volume (trillion rubles)	Growth rate (%)
2022	2,73	3100	8,46	—
2023	3,5	3400	11,9	+28%
2024*	—	—	13,7*	+15%*
2025*	—	—	15,8*	+15%*

Statistical table of changes

Note: Data for 2024–2025 are forecast.

Simple forecasting model: We use the geometric progression model to estimate future volumes:

$$V_n = V_0 \times (1 + r)^n$$

Where:

$V_0 = 11.9$ (trillion rubles in 2023)

$r = 0.15$ (annual growth rate)

$n =$ number of years

Then:

$$V_1 = 11.9 \times 1.15 = 13.7 \text{ (for 2024)}$$

$$V_2 = 13.7 \times 1.15 = 15.8 \text{ (for 2025)}$$

Conclusion

Thus, if the growth rate continues, the volume of e-commerce in Russia will exceed 15 trillion rubles by 2025, which will create conditions for increasing the share of online trade in the country's GDP.

The development of e-commerce has a significant impact on changing consumer behavior and the economic structure. Digital trading platforms are becoming not only sales channels, but also centers for analytics, personalized communications, and marketing strategies. As a result, shopping convenience increases, transaction costs decrease, and competition between companies intensifies.

The analysis showed that in the digital economy, there is a steady growth in online sales, an expansion of the customer base, and active implementation of innovations in the process of interaction with the consumer. Statistical forecasts demonstrate further growth in market volumes, as well as an increase in employment in the e-commerce sector.

These processes create a solid foundation for further growth of the digital sector, increased market transparency, and sustainable development of the national economy. It is important for businesses to adapt to these changes, invest in digital infrastructure, and focus on the needs of the modern consumer.

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